

An assessment on climate change among college students of St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA) amidst the Covid-19 pandemic

Belinda A. Liwanag ■ Michael D. Lee

Abstract

At this time of Covid-19 pandemic, developing countries such as the Philippines is still in the high risk of possible effects of climate change due to its climate-sensitive economy and low adaptive capacities. As the country is under dual threat: the adverse effects Covid-19 and enduring climate change crisis. With this, the online class for a semester is a good way to continue educating students about the effects and causes of climate change. Thus, this study aims to assess knowledge, perception, and the level of awareness on climate change of college students amidst the Covid-19 pandemic. The method used was quantitative and was participated by 135 college students. The instrument used was a validated online survey questionnaire with structured close-and open-ended questions concerning the factors that led students to acquire knowledge, perception, and awareness on climate change. The data was analyzed using the following statistical treatment and techniques: Frequency Count and Percentage, Percent and rank, weighted mean and One-way analysis of variance. And the results indicate that students in all year levels are all highly knowledgeable of climate change, wherein they described climate change as rising of temperature of the earth (84.4%) that brought extreme typhoons (83.7%), and rising sea level (78.5%). The students mostly acquired their knowledge on climate change through the online classes (39.3%), social media (26.7%), and rarely in their family and relatives (1.5%). The grand mean for students' perceptions towards Climate Change is 4.69 and the extent of awareness on the causes, effect, and action related to Climate Change has a grand mean of 4.29, which indicates strong awareness. Moreover, the study revealed that knowledge, perception, and level of awareness were not influenced by year level, sex, age, and degree program. Hence, it is concluded that online class on environmental science, which includes related topics like global warming, El Nino, and La Nina in the curriculum has an integral role in raising effective awareness and knowledge on mitigation measures towards climate change. The study recommends the use of qualitative method to further improve the study. Additionally, it can be presented as a project study proposal to the municipality for the local government units for its socio-environmental research projects.

Keywords: Climate change. Covid-19 pandemic. College students.

Belinda A. Liwanag*

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
belinda_liwanag@sdca.edu.ph

Michael D. Lee

University of Santo Tomas Graduate School, Manila, Philippines
michael.lee.gs@ust.edu.ph

*Corresponding author

Introduction

Climate change is a global issue that has dominated global development policy in recent years and continues to do so now. Millions of people's human rights, such as their rights to life, health, food, and water, are affected by climate change (Wewerinke & Yu, 2010). Because of their low adaptive capacities and the projected impacts of climate change, developing countries are more vulnerable to climate change than developed countries, according to a consensus. This is due to the predominance of rain-fed agriculture in their economies, the scarcity of capital for adaptation measures, their warmer baseline climates, and their heightened exposure to extreme weather events (Nzeadibe et al., 2011). As a result, it is expected that climate change would have far-reaching consequences for developing countries, particularly in terms of their ability to achieve sustainable development (UNFCCC, 2007 as cited by Barreda, 2018). Because it is strongly dependent on climate-sensitive economic operations such as agriculture and has fewer resources to adjust socially, technologically, and monetarily, the Philippines, as a developing country, is extremely vulnerable to the effects of climate change (Barreda, 2018).

The Philippines has comprehensive laws to promote environmental awareness like the Republic Act No. 9512 (RA 9512), known as the "National Environmental Awareness and Education Act of 2008" (Arellano Law Foundation, 2008) and the Climate Change Act of 2009, Philippine Republic Act (Republic Act 9729), an act mainstreaming climate change into government policy formulations, establishing the frameworks strategy and program on climate change and creating a climate changes commission. With these laws on climate change, public awareness of climate change in the Philippines has been a long-time part of daily lives of the Filipinos at home, workplaces, and schools. It is in schools where they are supposedly taught the higher knowledge on environmental awareness. Moreover, it is observed that students having acquired the knowledge about environment issues have the difficulties to act and practice some proper attitudes and norms on how to contribute to help lessen the effects of climate change.

On the positive note, UNESCO (n.d.) stated that education is a critical component of the global climate change response. It promotes "climate literacy" among young people, stimulates changes in their attitudes and behavior, and assists them in adapting to climate change-related trends. Likewise, Halady and Rao (2010), stated that awareness of the climate change phenomena leads to considerable behavioral changes, alleviating the potential and current hazards of climate change. This study believes that it is critical to ensure lifelong pro-environmental conduct among future citizens of the country by effectively disseminating knowledge and awareness at the college level, because these students are the heirs of the environment and will be the future educators of the country about environmental awareness on climate change. Similarly, the country's future customers would be affected by environmental sustainability challenges as a result of their consumption patterns.

At this time of Covid-19 pandemic, developing countries such as the Philippines is still in the high risk of the possible effects of climate change due to its climate-sensitive economy and low adaptive capacities. With this, the online class for a semester is a good way to continue educating students about the effects and causes of climate change. Thus, this study aims to assess knowledge, perception, and the level of awareness on climate change of college students amidst the Covid-19 pandemic.

Objectives

This study aimed to create an action plan based on the assessed the knowledge, perception and level of awareness on climate change among college students of St. Dominic College of Asia amidst the Covid-19 pandemic.

It specifically aims to:

1. Determine the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex;
 - 1.2. Age;
 - 1.3. Degree Program;
 - 1.4. Year Level.
2. Determine the climate change knowledge in terms of:
 - 2.1. The observed possible effects;
 - 2.2. Sources of climate change information;
 - 2.3. The cause of climate changes the respondents experienced in the past.
3. Determine the extent of awareness in terms of:
 - 3.1. causes, effect and actions as assessed by the respondents that are related to climate change;
 - 3.2. perceptions towards climate change.
4. Identify if significant difference exists when grouped according to profile in terms of
 - 4.1. the extent of awareness in causes, effects and actions; and
 - 4.2. perceive information towards climate change.

Methodology

Study Site

The study was conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia (SDCA), Bacoor City, Cavite. SDCA is mandated to revolutionize education by providing advanced instructions and proper training in the field of health science-related programs, arts, philosophy, education, business, computer studies, hotel and tourism management. This institution also extends its mandate to provide basic and advanced research, extension and linkages accord to the program it offers.

The institution has a total of 2,330 students distributed across its four different schools (School of Health Science Professions, School of Arts, Sciences and Education, School of Business and Computer Studies, and School of Hospitality and Tourism Management).

Before the study and data collection was carried-out, proper standards were met. Researchers provided letter of permission to all concerned officials such course-instructor/professor. Further, participation to this study were voluntary and prospect participants have the will to withdraw and refuse. In the online survey forms, information about the study, general objectives as well as its data confidentiality were clearly stated.

Survey and data gathering procedures

Due to the enhanced restrictions brought by the COVID-19 Pandemic, this study used an online survey questionnaire with structured close-and open-ended questions with three relevant sections: (1) personal identification, (2) Knowledge, Perception and Level of Awareness towards Climate Change, (3) Recommendations for possible action plans. This is to suffice the needs to assess the knowledge, perception, and level of awareness on Climate Change. This online survey was pre-tested and validated by specialized professors in the field of Environmental Science to determine the ease of facilitation as well as its validity. Google form was used to accurately record the answers of the participants.

The participants were chosen conveniently through spreading the online forms using social media and educational platforms such as Facebook, Google Mail, and Blackboard. Respondents were limited in Undergraduate students enrolled in St. Dominic College of Asia across various programs. Survey questions were composed in English translation to accommodate all respondents and assure their understanding since SDCA is a diverse community with foreign and local students.

Data Evaluation

Descriptive statistics like frequency distribution, mean and percentages were employed to summarize and analyzed the collected data. For data analyses, cross-tabulation test was used to determine the significant relationship between level of awareness and other variables.

The cross-tabulation test was used to show and visually interpret the frequency distribution for the knowledge, and level of awareness among tertiary students using 4 type factors (sex, age, year level, and program currently enrolled).

Eliciting student's knowledge and level of awareness

The respondent's knowledge about climate change was elicited via questionnaires answerable by Yes or No. On the other hand, level of awareness was assessed through questions regarding causes, effects, and actions relevant to climate change using five-point Likert Scale where:

- 4.20-5.00 – Strongly Agree
- 3.40-4.19 – Agree
- 2.60-3.39 – Do not know
- 1.80-2.59 – Disagree
- 1.00-1.79 – Strongly Disagree

Eliciting student's perception

Undergraduate respondents answered questions attuned to their stand on climate change-related statements. Questionnaire used a five-point Likert Scale, where:

- 4.20-5.00 – Strongly Agree
- 3.40-4.19 – Agree
- 2.60-3.39 – Do not know
- 1.80-2.59 – Disagree
- 1.00-1.79 – Strongly Disagree

Results and Discussion

Due to the restrictions amplified by the COVID-19 pandemic, there are several positive and negative impacts towards our environment (Rume & Islam, 2020). When global outbreak of coronavirus disease last 2019, numerous implemented lockdowns were ordained by the government which helps the environment to flourish and partially back to its normal condition, studies found that there are significantly increase in the air quality, reduction of the greenhouse gases emission, and reduces exploitation of tourist destination (Khan & Shah, 2021). However, the extended impact of climate change combined with COVID-19 pandemic cause economic shock and severe risks in health and society (Barouki et al., 2021; Filho et al., 2021). With this, it is important to determine whether tertiary students are aware to the impact of climate change amidst the current pandemic.

The Profile of the Respondent

Table 1. The frequency distribution of the respondents' profile in terms of different variables (n=135)

	Variable	F	%
Sex	Female	98	72.6
	Male	37	27.4
Age	16-19	61	45.2
	20-23	65	48.1
	24 above	9	6.7
Year Level	1st year	76	56.3
	2nd year	38	28.1
	3rd year	12	8.9
	4th year	7	5.2
	TVL Senior High School	1	0.7
	N/A	1	0.7
College Program	BS Accountancy	5	3.7
	BS Information Technology	10	7.4
	BS Psychology	8	5.9
	BS Public Administration	1	0.7
	Business	24	17.8
	Education	19	14.1
	Health Sciences	21	15.6
	Humanities	4	3.0
	Media and Communication	4	3.0
	Pharmacy	1	0.7
	Science Technology and Society	1	0.7
	Social Science	33	24.4
	Tourism Management	1	0.7
	TVL Senior High School	1	0.7
	N/A	2	1.5

This table shows the distribution of respondents across different variables such as sex, age, degree program, and year level of college students in St. Dominic College of Asia. As presented, more than half of the respondents were females (72.6%); ages 20-23 years old (48.1%). Domination of college Dominican female respondents in this study supports the data that among other group of individuals in the society, females are one of the most vulnerable groups when it comes to the adaptation and impact of climate change (Ballew et al., 2018; Halton, 2018). Hence, there are more interested female respondents. Furthermore, it implies that the institution must formulate a comprehensive action plan that is gender-sensitive and inclusive when it comes to climate change. Everyone is affected in the effect of climate change but male and female have different roles, status, and capabilities that can make to alleviate the on-going crisis. Thus, action plan should be well-represented by both genders to improve actions against climate change.

Supplementary, it was also revealed that most of the respondents came from first year level (56.3%) rather than on other higher levels and most are under Social Sciences program (24.4%). This shows that young people are generally not a passive victim, they organize their own environmental movements in school and community.

Respondents' Climate Change Knowledge

Most of the students both in Senior High School (SHS) and College claimed to be generally knowledgeable and aware about climate change. When they asked to identify the observed possible effects of climate change, students who knew what climate change often observed evidence such as rising temperature (84.4%), recurrence of stronger and intense typhoons (83.7%) and rising sea level (78.5%) (Table 2).

The Observed Possible Effects

Table 2. The frequency distribution of the respondents' climate change knowledge in terms of the observed possible effects (n=135)

Possible Effects	f	%	Rank
Varying climate	98	72.6	4th
Stronger and Intense Typhoons	113	83.7	2nd
Rising of Temperature	114	84.4	1st
Rising of Sea Level	106	78.5	3rd
Insect Infestation	50	37.0	10th
Shifting of Wet and Dry Patterns	97	71.9	5th
Animal Extinction	79	58.5	8th
Habitat Loss	89	69.9	6th
Diversity Loss	81	60	7th
Less Crop Yield	77	57	9th
Others	5	3.45	11th

Involvement of students in topic such as climate change amidst pandemic has huge part in increasing the capacity of young individuals to adapt and think for a mitigation strategy against climate change impacts (Barreda, 2018). Relying on this result, Dominican college students are highly knowledgeable that climate change is real and currently happening. Hence, importance of environmental education is necessary to be more aware and knowledgeable regarding the extent effect and observed evidence of climate change. Through this, Dominican students can participate in educating its citizenry of local communities in raising awareness on climate change.

Sources of Climate Change Information

Out of different observed evidence and knowledge towards climate change, thirty-nine percent of the students received this information from school followed by the power of social media (26.7%). However, there are only 0.7% gained information inside their households. Results indicated that the school has highest source of information related and relevant to climate change. It is imperative to have a well-structured curriculum that further enhance the topic towards environmental education.

Table 3. The frequency distribution of the respondents' climate change knowledge in terms of the sources of climate change information (n=135)

Sources of Climate Change Information	f	%	Rank
Family and relatives	1	0.7	6th
Television and Radio	26	19.3	3rd
Scientific journals	17	12.6	4th
Social media	36	26.7	2nd
School	53	39.3	1st
Others	2	1.5	5th

Education has the power to cultivate the mind of young individuals in understanding the variables that affect climate change (Bofferding & Kloser, 2013); having a strong knowledge and level of awareness towards climate change can help in raising awareness in numerous platforms such as in social media, news, conference meeting, and social gatherings. Further, it can help formulating mitigation and adaptation strategies that can help not only for carrying-out institutional and program-based activities, but it can also decipher information to its local communities.

On the other hand, social media has the power to positively encourage mobilization of climate change activists, mediates knowledge gap and a safe space for discussing the issues regarding the extent effect, and what affects climate change not only in the environment but as well as to our economy (Anderson, 2017). For instance, according to the studies of Zhao (2009) and Mavrodieva et al. (2019), social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram have a huge part in mediating the information gap and changing public's perception towards climate change. In line with the result of this study, St. Dominic College of Asia being one of the Digital campuses in Cavite has an advantage in making its students more aware of what is happening around them especially in topics such as environmental education due to its accessibility to internet connection and user-friendly research databases.

The cause of climate changes the respondents experienced in the past

Climate change still one of the most debated topics, in fact oftentimes individuals still believed that climate change is a myth and never considered as a deep-felt reality (Carter, 2007). However, there are numerous studies support that this phenomenon is real, observable, and currently happening with adverse impact in the environment and in areas whether rural or urban (Kabir et al., 2016; Nzeadibe et al., 2011; Tirivagansi & Nyahunda, 2019). In the Philippines which is considered as a climate-sensitive country which main means of income came from agriculture and fisheries, the impact of climate change can drastically change someone's everyday living. Hence, one of the questions inquired to students was their experiences in the past that they believed entailed by climate change, results revealed that they believed was associated with climate change are rising temperature (66.7%), occurrence of extreme typhoons (65.9%), large wildfires (19.3%) and changes in the dry and wet patterns (3.19%).

Table 4. The frequency distribution of the respondents' climate change knowledge in terms of the cause of climate changes experienced in the past

Experiences Caused by Climate Change	f	%	Rank
Extreme Typhoons	89	65.9	2nd
Rising of Temperature	90	66.7	1st
Insect Infestation	11	8.1	6th
Prevalence of Disease	19	14.1	5th
Frequency of Large Wildfires	26	19.3	4th
Change in Dry and Wet Patterns	43	3.19	3rd
Massive Flood	1	0.7	7th

The result of this study can be attributed to the increased incidence of severe typhoons that recently hit the country amidst the current pandemic. Since St. Dominic College of Asia is near coastal area, students are highly knowledgeable in terms of their observed experiences happening around them. Additionally, Dominican students participate in different institutional-driven environmental activities such as clean-up drive, tree planting, and environmental awareness seminar and webinars despite under pandemic.

With this, Dominican student's role in environmental awareness has a considerable impact on the on-going current crisis. In making a proposed action plan, it is essential to use their knowledge and their recommendations to alleviate the problem by creating a program specific to Climate Change for they are also the ones with the ability and access to social media and other media platforms.

The Extent of Awareness on Climate Change

Causes, Effects, and Actions Related to Climate Change

Respondents were also inquired regarding the causes, effects and actions that are related to Climate Change. Responses suggested that they are aware that continuous deforestation (4.52), and combustion of fossil fuels (4.44) which all boils down to the harmful human activities (4.53) which are said to be the main cause of climate change.

These lead to possible effects on human health (4.69), poor harvest and extreme crop loss (4.52) as well as increase in sea level (4.50). However, due to the effort of the Dominican community together with the Community Extension and Services (CESO) of St. Dominic College of Asia, they are aware that the possible actions that can alleviate this problem are tree planting (4.61), and proper garbage segregation (4.47).

Table 5. The mean distribution of the respondents' assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of causes, effect, and actions related to climate change (n=135)

Causes, Effects, and Actions Related to Climate Change	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Climate Change is caused by deforestation and illegal logging.	4.52	SA
2. Climate Change is caused by the combustion of fossil fuels.	4.44	SA
3. Climate Change is the root of powerful typhoons.	4.13	A
4. Climate Change can cause poor harvest and extreme crop loss.	4.52	SA
5. Planting trees can prevent climate change.	4.61	SA
6. Becoming a smart buyer/consumer can be an effective way in fighting climate change.	4.31	SA
7. Climate Change can lead to food shortage.	4.41	SA
8. The 3R (Reuse, reduce, and recycle) can stop/reduce the effect of climate change.	4.47	SA
9. Climate change is a threat to human health.	4.69	SA
10. Climate change can be traced to the loss of flora and fauna.	4.04	A
11. Destruction of corals is caused by climate change.	3.74	A
12. Climate change is caused by a high incidence of forest fire.	3.98	A
13. Climate change is caused by a high incidence of tropical diseases.	3.69	A
14. Using environmentally sound products can help prevent climate change.	4.05	A
15. Climate change is more harmful than beneficial.	4.50	SA
16. Climate change is mostly brought by human activities.	4.53	SA
17. Climate change causes a rise in sea level.	4.50	SA
18. Climate change leads to coastal erosion.	4.24	SA
19. Climate change leads to economic problems.	4.38	SA
20. Climate change is the main reason for ocean acidification.	4.08	A
Grand Mean	4.29	SA

Range of Interpretation: SD:1.0-1.80; D1.81-2.60; N:2.61-3.40; A: 3.41-4.20; SA: 4.21-5.0

Perceptions towards Climate Change

Table 6. The mean distribution of the respondents' assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of perceptions towards climate change

Causes, Effects, and Actions Related to Climate Change	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Climate Change is happening now.	4.69	SA
Climate change should be an urgent and immediate concern.	4.80	SA
Climate Change is a threat /problem in achieving Sustainable Development Goals.	4.39	SA
We need to formulate and establish stronger laws that protect the environment.	4.56	SA
We need to integrate environmental topics education as promotion of climate change is important.	4.70	SA
Climate Change can affect everyone regardless of status, age, gender, race, etc.	4.62	SA
Climate change prevention requires the collective effort of the community.	4.73	SA
There are climate change agencies on both a national and global scale that I know.	3.98	A
Our government response to climate change crises is adequate.	3.28	N
Failure to forecast weather events daily is brought by climate change.	3.39	A
Public information on weather and climate situations may raise awareness on climate change.	4.49	SA
Joining environmental organizations may improve my awareness of fighting climate change.	4.56	SA
The use of social media can help the level of awareness on climate change issues.	4.55	SA
Grand Mean	4.69	SA

Range of Interpretation: SD:1.0-1.80; D1.81-2.60; N:2.61-3.40; A: 3.41-4.20; SA: 4.21-5.0

Understanding the perception of students towards climate change is considered as an important tool to determine and analyze the insights of a particular individual in understanding a particular environmental issue (Dewi & Khoirunisa, 2018; Lombardi & Sinatra, 2012; Prasad & Mkumbachi, 2021). Students were also asked towards their perception in climate change, it revealed that they are strongly aware that climate change is happening right now (4.69) which is an urgent and immediate concern that our environment is currently facing (4.80), and it needs a collective effort of the community (4.73) to prevent the effects of climate change.

Apart from that, Dominican students believed that integration of relative environmental topics to curriculum and joining environmental organizations could enhance the knowledge and awareness of students with regards to climate change (4.70). Hence, the proposed action plan that the institution must formulate should aligned in the recommendations given by the students to further fortify the already aware Dominican students.

The significant difference exists when grouped according to profile in terms of the extent of awareness in causes, effects, and actions and perceiving information towards climate change

Table 7. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of causes, effects, and actions when grouped according to sex

Sex	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Male	4.24	SA	0.590	0.444	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
Female	4.31	SA				

Table 8. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of causes, effects, and actions when grouped according to age

Age	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
16-19	4.41	SA	2.90	0.059	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
20-23	4.21	SA				
24 and above	4.12	A				

Table 9. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of causes, effects, and actions when grouped according to degree program

Degree Program	Mean	VI	f	p	Decision	Remarks
BS Accountancy	4.31	SA	0.691	0.780	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
BS Information Technology	4.31	SA				
BS Psychology	4.23	SA				
BS Public Administration	3.95	A				
Business	4.41	SA				
Education	4.04	A				
Health Sciences	4.35	SA				
Humanities	4.36	SA				
Media and Communication	4.38	SA				
Pharmacy	5.00	SA				
Science, Technology and Society	4.25	SA				
Social Science	4.26	SA				
Tourism Management	4.65	SA				
TVL Senior High School	4.45	SA				
N/A	4.63	SA				

Table 10. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on climate change in terms of causes, effects, and actions when grouped according to year level

Year Level	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
1st year	4.31	SA	0.461	0.805	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
2nd year	4.25	SA				
3rd year	4.36	SA				
4th year	4.32	SA				
TVL Senior High School	4.45	SA				
N/A	3.60	A				

To determine whether individual’s knowledge towards the cause, effect, and actions on climate change are influenced by their demographic profile, the researchers grouped the respondents based on their age, sex, program currently enrolled, and year level. Results revealed that there is no significant difference in all demographic profile that were assessed.

For so many years, gender dynamics has been part of assessing the knowledge and perception towards climate change, data revealed a contrasting result provided by some scientific literacy research wherein women are more knowledgeable and slightly concern on climate change than men do in United States (McCright, 2010). Supplementarily, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) supports the data that women are more knowledgeable towards climate change since they are the one that is highly vulnerable and affected to the extent effect of climate change for, they are the ones that is less represented due to patriarchal notion (IUCN, 2015).

Table 11. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on perceiving information towards climate change when grouped according to sex

Sex	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Male	4.32	SA	0.264	0.608	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
Female	4.38	SA				

Table 12. The comparison of means of the respondents’ assessment on the extent of awareness on perceiving information towards climate change when grouped according to age

Age	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
16-19	4.41	SA	0.470	0.626	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
20-23	4.32	SA				
24 and above	4.31	A				

Table 13. The comparison of means of the respondents' assessment on the extent of awareness on perceiving information towards climate change when grouped according to degree program

Degree Program	Mean	VI	f	p	Decision	Remarks
BS Accountancy	3.99	A	1.113	0.354	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
BS Information Technology	4.12	A				
BS Psychology	4.32	SA				
BS Public Administration	4.15	A				
Business	4.49	SA				
Education	4.37	SA				
Health Sciences	4.39	SA				
Humanities	3.67	A				
Media and Communication	4.50	SA				
Pharmacy	4.00	A				
Science, Technology and Society	4.69	SA				
Social Science	4.46	SA				
Tourism Management	4.54	SA				
TVL Senior High School	4.54	SA				
N/A	4.35	SA				

Table 14. The comparison of means of the respondents' assessment on the extent of awareness on perceiving information towards climate change when grouped according to year level

Year Level	Mean	VI	f-computed	p-value	Decision	Remarks
1st year	4.35	SA	0.346	0.884	Accept the Null Hypothesis	Not Significant
2nd year	4.42	SA				
3rd year	4.40	SA				
4th year	4.15	A				
TVL Senior High School	4.54	SA				
N/A	4.31	SA				

As the world continues rallying for a long-lasting solution for a global environmental problem like this, another strategy to come-up with a well-structured action plan specifically for an institution as to responding to climate change is through assessing the extent of awareness of students' perceived information towards climate change (Barreda, 2018). In determining whether respondent's demographic profile can affect respondent's awareness, the researchers grouped the respondents based on their age, sex, program currently enrolled, and year level. Same with above results, it revealed that there is no significant difference in all demographic profile that were assessed.

Results implicit that the institutional-based programs, and environmental education curriculum gave the students the necessary information regarding climate change regardless their sex, age, programs, and year level even though our current situation is under pandemic and conducting distance learning.

Conclusion

The results indicate that students in all year levels are highly knowledgeable of climate change, wherein they described climate change as rising of temperature of the earth (84.4%) that brought extreme typhoons (83.7%) and rising sea level (78.5%). The students mostly acquired their knowledge on climate change through the online classes (39.3%), social media (26.7%), and rarely in their family and relative (1.5%). The grand mean for students' perceptions towards Climate Change is 4.69, and the extent of awareness on the causes, effect, and action related to Climate Change has a grand mean of 4.29 which indicates strong awareness. Moreover, the study revealed that knowledge, perception, and level of awareness were not influenced by year level, sex, age and degree program. The online class on environmental science which include related topics like global warming, El Nino, and La Nina in the curriculum has an integral role in raising effective awareness and knowledge on mitigation measures towards climate change.

Recommendation

The study recommends the use of qualitative method to further improve the study. Also, assessing the level of awareness, knowledge, and perception of other respondents in the grade school, middle school and senior high school is recommended. Additionally, the study can be presented as a project study proposal to the municipality for the local government units for its socio-environmental research projects.

References

- Anderson, A. A. (2017). Effects of social media use on climate change opinion, knowledge, and behavior. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Climate Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190228620.013.369>
- Barreda, A. B. (2018). Assessing the level of awareness on climate change and sustainable development among students of Partido State University, Camarines Sur, Philippines. *Journal of Sustainability Education, 17*. http://www.susted.com/wordpress/content/assessing-the-level-of-awareness-on-climate-change-and-sustainable-development-among-students-of-partido-state-university-camarines-sur-philippines_2018_03/
- Barouki, R., Kogevinas, M., Audouze, K., Belesova, K., Bergman, A., Birnbaum, L., Boekhold, S., Denys, B., Desseille, C., Drakvik, E., Frumkin, H., Garric, J., Destoumieux-Garzon, D., Haines, A., Huss, A., Jensen, G., Karakitsios, S., Klanova, J., Koskela, A., ... & HERA-COVID-19 working group. (2021). The COVID-19 pandemic and global environmental change: Emerging research needs. *Environment International, 146*, 106272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106272>
- Ballew, M., Marlon, J., Leiserowitz, A., & Maibach, E. (2018). *Gender differences in public understanding of climate change*. Yale Program on Climate Change Communication. <https://climatecommunication.yale.edu/publications/gender-differences-in-public-understanding-of-climate-change/>

- Bofferding, L., & Kloser, M. (2014). Middle and high school students' conceptions of climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies. *Environmental Education Research, 21*(2), 275-294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504622.2014.888401>
- Carter, R. M. (2007). The myth of dangerous human-caused climate change. *Proceedings of the AusIMM New Leaders' Conference, 25*, 61-74. <https://researchonline.jcu.edu.au/3130/>
- Congress of the Philippines. (2008, December 12). *Republic Act No. 9512 – An act to promote environmental awareness through environmental education and for other purposes*. Official Gazette. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2008/12/12/republic-act-no-9512/>
- Congress of the Philippines. (2008, December 12). *Republic Act No. 9729 – An act mainstreaming climate change into government policy formulations, establishing the framework strategy and program on climate change, creating for this purpose the climate change commission, and for other purposes*. Official Gazette. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2008/12/12/republic-act-no-9512/>
- Dewi, R. P., & Khoirunisa, N. (2018). Middle school student's perception of climate change at Boyolali District, Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 200*, 012061. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/200/1/012061>
- Filho, W. L., Wall, T., Alves, F., Nagy, G. J., Carril, L. R. F., Li, C., Mucova, S., Joost, J. P., Rayman-Bacchus, L., Totin, E., Ayal, D. Y., Lütz, J. M., Azeiteiro, U. M., Vinuesa, A. G., & Minhas, A. (2021). The impacts of the early outset of the COVID-19 pandemic on climate change research: Implications for policy-making. *Environmental Science & Policy, 124*, 267-278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.06.008>
- Halady, I. R., & Rao, P. H. (2010). Does awareness to climate change lead to behavioral change? *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 2*(1), 6-22. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17568691011020229>
- Halton, M. (2018). *Climate Change 'impacts women more than men'*. BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-43294221>
- International Union for Conservation of Nature. (2015, November). *Gender and climate change*. <https://www.iucn.org/resources/issues-briefs/gender-and-climate-change>
- Kabir, M. I., Rahman, M. B., Smith, W., Lusha, M. A., Azim, S., & Milton, A. H. (2016). Knowledge and perception about climate change and human health: Findings from a baseline survey among vulnerable communities in Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health, 16*(1), 266. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-2930-3>
- Khan, I., Shah, D., & Shah, S. S. (2021). COVID-19 pandemic and its positive impacts on environment: an updated review. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology, 18*(2), 521-530. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-020-03021-3>
- Lombardi, D., & Sinatra, G. (2012). College students' perceptions about the plausibility of human-induced climate change. *Research in Science Education, 42*(2), 201-217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-010-9196-z>
- Mavrodieva, A. V., Rachman, O. K., Harahap, V. B., & Shaw, R. (2019). Role of social media as a soft power tool in raising public awareness and engagement in addressing climate change. *Climate, 7*(10), 122. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli7100122>
- McCright, A. M. (2010). The effects of gender on climate change knowledge and concern in the American public. *Population and Environment, 32*(1), 66-87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11111-010-0113-1>
- Nzeadibe, T. C., Egbule, C. L., Chukwuone, N. A., & Agu, V. C. (2011). *Climate change awareness and adaptation in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria* (Working Paper No. 57). African Technology Policy Studies Network. <https://media.africaportal.org/documents/wps57.pdf>
- Prasad, R. R., & Mkumbachi, R. L. (2021). University students' perceptions of climate change: The case study of the University of the South Pacific-Fiji Islands. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management, 13*(4/5), 416-434. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-12-2020-0126>
- Rume, T., & Islam, S. D. U. (2020). Environmental effects of COVID-19 pandemic and potential strategies of sustainability. *Heliyon, 6*(9), e04965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04965>
- Tirivangasi, H. M., & Nyahunda, L. (2019). Challenges faced by rural people in mitigating the effects of climate change in the Mazungunye communal lands, Zimbabwe. *Jambá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies, 11*(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v11i1.596>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (n.d.). *Education for climate action*. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-sustainable-development/cce>
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2007). *Climate change: Impacts, vulnerabilities and adaptation in developing countries*. UNFCCC. <http://unfccc.int/resource/docs/publications/impacts.pdf>
- Wewerinke, M., & Yu, V. P. B. (2010). *Addressing climate change through sustainable development and the promotion of human rights* (Research Paper, No. 34). South Centre. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/232152/1/south-centre-rp-034.pdf>
- Zhao, X. (2009). Media use and global warming perceptions: A snapshot of the reinforcing spirals. *Communication Research, 36*(5), 698-723. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0093650209338911>